

Mottweiler, H., Le Mouillour, I., & Annen, S. (2022). New forms of European VET governance in the interplay between the EU-ropean Labour Market and VET Policy? A governance analysis of the EU-ropean taxonomy of skills, competences, qualifications and occupations (Esco). In C. Nägele, N. Kersh, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Trends in vocational education and training research, Vol. V. Proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Research (ECER), Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 121–131). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6977267>

New Forms of European VET Governance in the Interplay Between the EU-Rocean Labour Market and Vet Policy? A Governance Analysis of the EU-Rocean Taxonomy of Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (Esco)

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Abstract

Context: The European Taxonomy of Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) has been developed over the last ten years, in particular with the aim of promoting worker mobility in Europe. With regard to the vocational training systems this raises the question of whether the effects of ESCO will remain limited to labour market mobility or whether the identification of skills needs as well as the definition of occupational skill profiles could also have an impact on the contents of national VET programs. This paper analyses the mechanisms of European governance in the inter-play between European labour market policy and VET policy within the ESCO development and implementation process.

Approach: Methodologically, this paper is based on (1) a document-analysis of European legal acts, resolutions and declarations in the context of the ESCO development and implementation. In order to reconstruct the ESCO governance with the respective roles, tasks and constellations of relevant actors at the national and supranational level, minutes and documents of central European bodies in the ESCO construction process are evaluated in a second step (2). These analyses are complemented by interviews conducted with actors in ESCO construction and ESCO implementation (3).

Findings: Preliminary results show a diverse interweaving of governance forms through binding legal acts, soft legislation and the financial support of implementation programs. On the one hand a rather hierarchical governance through regulations and decisions becomes visible. On the other hand, the coordination process between the European Commission and the member states also includes "soft" forms of coordination through consultation and negotiation.

Conclusion: The findings emphasize on the one hand the project logic of ESCO, on the other, a conflicting logic between education and labour market policy. Initial analyses suggest a greater depth of intervention of European education policy by linking labour market and education policy. In this respect, however, it will be important how and in which manner qualification profiles will be linked to the ESCO occupations and skills. This process has not yet been completed at the present time.

Keywords: Educational Governance, European VET Governance, ESCO

1 Introduction

The European Taxonomy of Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) has been developed over the last ten years, in particular with the aim of promoting worker mobility in Europe (European Commission, 2017; 2018). It intends to make a decisive contribution to this goal by providing Europe-wide comparability of occupations, competences and qualifications. In the context of the "Europe 2020" strategy, ESCO is supposed to provide a classification basis for the main instruments of the European labour market, namely EURES and EUROPASS.

The target groups of ESCO are in particular companies, individuals, training providers, as well as public and private employment service agencies. The main objective is to make formally or informally acquired competences visible, support the search for employment and offer demand-oriented training opportunities (European Commission, 2017). The EURES directive serves as a legal basis for the development and implementation of ESCO as a European-wide classification of occupations, qualifications and skills (c.f. chapter 2). Conversely, ESCO provides the underlying classification for the European employment portal EURES as well as for the EUROPASS. The latter is a portal for creating individual e-portfolios CVs and application letters. Furthermore, it is linked to the EURES portal and therefore offers a search function for jobs as well as qualification offers (cf. Figure 1).

Figure 1

Overview of the Relationship and Interconnection of EURES, ESCO and EUROPASS

Referring to the aim of using ESCO for supporting the identification of relevant skills, competencies, and qualifications it could potentially become a basis for curriculum development (Europäische Kommission, 2014; Winch, 2021). With regard to the national vocational training systems, this raises the question of whether the effects of ESCO will remain limited to labour market mobility or whether the identification of qualification and skills needs as well as the definition of occupational skill profiles could have an impact on the contents of national VET programs.

The interplay between labour market and education policy aspects, which addresses both national and supranational governance issues, is taken up in this paper. The aim of this contribution is to analyse mechanisms of European governance in the interplay between European labour market policy and VET policy. In this respect, a multi-level analysis of European VET governance is provided. This includes an analysis of which actors and which forms of coordination are relevant in the context of ESCO and how they interact with each other.

The main research questions are:

- Which forms of coordination and control are relevant for the development and implementation process of ESCO?
- To which extent does ESCO as a new transparency instrument lead to new forms of European VET governance – and in particular: Can ESCO be seen as a prototype of new European governance between "hard law" and "soft law"?

To address these questions, the theoretical frame of reference is presented in the second chapter. This is followed by a description of the methodological approach in chapter 3. Chapter 4 contains the research findings. The contribution is finalised by a conclusion in chapter 5.

2 Theoretical Framework

ESCO as a European project includes different forms of governance at the supranational level - and, beyond this, the respective networks of experts and institutions at the European and national levels. The ESCO development and implementation process addresses various governance issues in the interrelationship of national and supranational VET governance. This does not only include the question of the effects of this new transparency instrument on national VET systems on a practical level (Diekmann, 2020). Stakeholders are embedded in institutional regulatory structures, their constellation and modes of interactions evolve and within the ESCO development process committees and experts are becoming increasingly important (Lawn, 2019).

2.1 Coordination and Control

From a theoretical perspective, questions concerning relevant levels of governance as well as evolving coordination mechanisms emerge. Theoretical educational governance approaches lead our analysis of the different modes of coordination as well as the levels of control within the ESCO project.

Educational governance examines control processes in the education system with special consideration of the coordination of action within different actor constellations in complex multi-level systems (Strebel et al. 2019). In this context, diverse institutional regulatory structures and the way in which they become effective for action as well as their impact on the respective system are also considered (Kuhlee, 2017). In particular, the institutional regulatory structures, as well as the constellations of actors at the European and national level, are addressed. The main questions in this respect are which forms of coordination are significant in the context of ESCO and how they become effective.

With regard to the coordination of action as the core element of governance theory analyses, classical educational governance approaches distinguish between different concepts and modes of coordination. These include, among others, basic governance mechanisms of observation, influence and negotiation (Kussau & Brüsemeister, 2007; Schimank, 2007) as well as governance by hierarchy, market, community or network (Altrichter & Heinrich, 2007).

In the context of the ESCO development, this raises the question of the extent to which hierarchical control, e.g. through European legislation in the area of (vocational) education policy, exists or can become effective. In this regard, reference should be made to the principle of subsidiarity and the ban on harmonisation for education in general and VET in particular. VET remains in the remit of national authorities according to the relevant European legislation and

agreements; the diversity of VET systems in Europe stems from specific national or regional socio-economic and cultural factors and conditions. However, the strategic relevance of ESCO for labour market policy measures (and its possible impact on European and national labour markets) may mean that European legislation on VET gets in the long term less relevant. This would imply a shift in the mode of coordination or control of the actors.

Beyond hierarchical control, the governance concept integrates the coordination of action of state and non-state actors in the multi-level system. Since a large number of different actors and institutions at national and supranational levels have been and still are involved in the ESCO development process, this conceptual extension of governance is appropriate, going beyond the preoccupation with authoritarian-hierarchical control (Kussau & Brüsemeister, 2007). At the same time, a multi-level analysis that includes actors below as well as above the nation-state (Do Amaral, 2017) is particularly relevant for the question of the significance of supranational governance effects in the network of relationships between institutional actors and networks at the European and national level.

2.2 Multi-Level System

Educational governance theories (Schimank, 2007; Altrichter & Heinrich, 2007; Kussau & Brüsemeister, 2007) enable the identification of relevant governance levels in the context of ESCO and draw the multilevel framework. The concept of the multi-level system is to be understood as a conceptual culmination and summarising analytical reference point of institutionalised interdependent relationships between actors. (Kussau & Brüsemeister, 2007). The advantage of this concept consists in the inclusion of institutions and actors at different levels as well as their reciprocal relationships. In this regard, different dimensions or levels of multi-level systems are distinguished, for example, a subdivision according to formal levels (macro-, meso-, micro-level) (ibid.,32). For the following analyses in the ESCO construction and implementation process, the concept of "cross-border coordination" provides a better connection – addressing the division of responsibilities according to different levels and, at the same time, the need for coordination of action in the multi-level system (Benz, 2004; Kussau & Brüsemeister, 2007).

3 Methodological Approach

Methodologically, this paper is based on different methods of analysis.

In a first step, a document analysis of European legal acts, resolutions and declarations underlying the ESCO development and implementation is carried out. This analysis examines the significance of governance “qua hierarchy” through direct or indirect effects of binding legal acts (“hard law”). In addition, typical governance forms of “soft law” such as negotiation and competition systems (e.g. open method of coordination) are considered.

In order to reconstruct the ESCO governance with the respective roles, tasks and constellations of relevant actors at the national and supranational level, minutes and documents of central European bodies in the ESCO development process are evaluated in a second step. In this regard, the main actors with their respective tasks and areas of competence in the ESCO development- and implementation process are described. In order to identify relevant modes of coordination and control key actor constellations are analysed.

Additionally, for a more in-depth analysis of the governance processes in the ESCO development and implementation process, (to date) 20 qualitative semi-structured expert interviews

with ESCO Committee Members as well as national ESCO “Implementers”¹ were carried out and will be analysed in the following section². This also includes a qualitative analysis of stakeholder structures.

4 Preliminary Results

4.1 ESCO development: The interplay of European VET governance between “hard-law” and “soft-law”

In contrast to other areas of European policy and influence, European VET policy is – strictly speaking - not a clearly delineated policy field. Reasons are interfaces with other policy areas such as education, economy, labour market and social policy - and especially the national responsibility for VET, to which the subsidiarity principle and the ban on harmonisation apply.

The Treaty of Rome (1957) forms the basis for the development of a European approach to vocational training. Although the Treaty of Rome was primarily aimed at removing national barriers to trade and production, from 1959 onwards, it was a question of developing a European dimension in education, which, according to Charlier and Croché (2006), was reflected in the 1960s by the deployment of information campaigns and the drafting of ten principles linking VET to the objectives of common economic development. The Lisbon Strategy and in particular the decisions of the EU Council of Education Ministers in Copenhagen (2002) have enhanced the EU’s vocational education and training policy, but at the cost of increasing subordination to the aspect of job security and employability.

Despite the lack of a direct European competence for VET, many European legal acts have direct or indirect impacts on VET via interfaces to other policy areas. The European legal acts differ systematically and range from “hard law” to programmatic steering instruments that are not legal acts in the narrower sense. In the area of “soft law” in particular, there are steering instruments such as recommendations, opinions, resolutions and action programmes. Implementation by the respective EU member states takes place on a voluntary basis. However, other coordination mechanisms apply here, in particular the Open Method of Coordination (OMC) and the European Semester. The OMC is characterised by steering based on key objectives with a realisation plan including defined indicators in connection with country comparisons and monitoring processes for the implementation of the formulated objectives. In this context, steering takes place via competition and, in particular, via negotiation systems, for example in the form of best practices and benchmarks (Bohlinger, 2019).

Analysing the impact of *hierarchical forms of governance* (“hard law”) in the context of ESCO development the underlying legal regulations of the ESCO development process are documented in the following part.

The fundamental principles of the ESCO development are to be found in the *Eures Regulation (EU) 2016/589* in combination with the *Implementing Decisions 2018/1020* and *2018/1021*. The *Regulation 2016/589* on a European Employment Services Network (EURES) includes the development of a European classification as a “standard terminology of occupations, skills, competences and qualifications”. This European classification, in the later development process called ESCO, serves as an important basis for IT-supported employment

¹ In particular, committee members and ESCO implementers from the countries selected in this research project (Germany, Poland, Ireland and Latvia) were identified and recruited. In addition, further European key actors were identified. The sampling strategy was based on accessible information from the evaluated committee minutes. In addition, (contact) information from interviews already conducted was used.

² This paper provides an interim analysis with preliminary results. In this regard, it should be noted that the evaluations at this stage especially reflect the perspective of German committee members. Additional Expert Interviews are currently being conducted.

services and the IT platform to be set up for this purpose. It is supplemented by the *Implementing Decisions 2018/1020* and *2018/1021* establishing the technical standards and formats to ensure automatic matching and interoperability between national systems and the European classification (cf. Table 1).

Table 6
European legal bases of ESCO construction

	Legal Act/legal form	Content/ESCO reference (direct/indirect)
Legal basis for ESCO implementation		
Regulation (EU) 2016/589 on a European network of employment services (EURES), workers' access to mobility services and the further integration of labour markets	Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Organisation of the EURES network ▶ Development of common IT platform ▶ Development of European classification as standard terminology of occupations, skills, competences and qualifications to facilitate online job search within the Union ▶ Automated matching via the common IT platform.
Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/1020 on the adoption and updating of the list of skills, competences and occupations of the European classification for the purpose of automated matching through the EURES common IT platform	Decision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Determination of the list of skills, competences and occupations of the European Classification ▶ Definitions of terms, including knowledge, skills, competences, occupation; ESCO service platform (Article 1) ▶ Ensure, make available and update the list of skills, competences and occupations of the European classification on the ESCO service platform through EURES (Article 4)
Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/1021 on the adoption of technical standards and formats necessary for the operation of the automated matching through the common IT platform using the European classification and the interoperability between national systems and the European classification	Decision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Definitions (Article 2) ▶ Creation of matching tables for the comparison between national, regional and sector-specific classifications and the European classification ▶ Ensuring interoperability with the common IT platform through matching tables (Article 4) ▶ Management and updating of the technical standards and formats (Article 6)

In addition, ESCO is also the subject of non-binding resolutions, opinions and action programmes that are to be located in the *area of "soft law"*. This especially includes the "Europe 2020" action programmes and the New Skills Agenda for Europe. In this regard, ESCO is associated with the "New Skills for new Jobs" initiative within the framework of the Europe 2020 Strategy for Growth and Jobs. This was adopted in 2010 as a follow-up programme to the Lisbon Strategy for a period of ten years. Direct references exist in particular with regard to the work areas on "improving the representation and comparability of competences and qualifications" and on "improving the collection of data on competences". ESCO is also mentioned in the opinion "Action Plan for Digital Literacy" (2018/C 461/08) and in the recommendation on the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning (2018/C 307/10).

A further governance aspect at the level of implementation is located in the field of *EU-funded programme support*. An important example in this context is the "Sector Skill Alliances". The aim is to develop European skills strategies in key economic sectors, selected on the basis of policy priorities, the definition of a clear sectoral strategy for skills and jobs, the maturity of the sector's growth strategy, and stakeholder participation and engagement. This includes, inter alia, the development of a sectoral skills and competences strategy, the

development of occupational profiles, vocational training programmes and qualifications, and the design of a long-term action plan to be rolled out at national and regional levels. In addition, the use of all EU (transparency) instruments, i.e. EQF, EQAVET and ESCO, will be promoted (European Commission, 2020). ESCO acts as an important reference for the recognition of specific sectoral competences, but also of the transversal competences required for the development of the sector (ibid.). In the 2020 European recommendation on VET (2020/C 417/01) ESCO should contribute to mobility as well as to qualification recognition processes and supportive of the deployment of Europass.

Concluding, the first part of the governance analyses in the ESCO context shows the diverse interweaving of forms of governance through binding legal acts, soft legislation and the financial promotion of action programmes, which are intended to support the development and implementation of this platform. It becomes clear that in particular through the linking of labour market and education policy – in this case through the linking of ESCO and EURES - a greater degree of intervention through binding legal acts (EURES Regulation with Implementing Decisions) becomes apparent. Usually, European VET policy rather tends to move within the framework of "soft legislation". For a further analysis of the interrelationships, the different actors and institutions in the ESCO constitutional process at the national and supranational level with their respective tasks and roles will be examined in more detail in the following chapter.

4.2 ESCO-Governance: Actor constellations, tasks and coordination

Actor constellations and tasks

With regard to ESCO governance, the different actors and constellations of actors are examined. The Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion of the European Commission plays a central role in the development, implementation and updating of the ESCO classification. Initial interview results emphasize the Role of DG Employment: “*It started as an idea of DG Employment, and it continued as a project or even a tool that is coordinated, steered by DG Employment*” (Member ESCO Board, 01). In this respect, interviewees mention the subordinate role of DG Education. The EURES regulation (“hard law”) is seen as an important aspect of the steering processes of ESCO: the ESCO implementation took on a legally binding character (Members ESCO Membership Working group, 07, 09; Member ESCO Maintenance Committee, 06).

In the process of ESCO development, DG Employment was supported by various stakeholders, as well as the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (Cedefop). A steering group was set with the ESCO Management Board, the ESCO Secretariat and four reference groups, subordinated to the European Commission. These central actors of ESCO governance are presented below and classified according to their (steering) function.

On a *strategic political level*, the *ESCO Board* (2011 – 2017) provided advice to the Commission. It included various experts from the Member States, e.g. ministries, representatives of the EQF Advisory Board, employers' organisations, as well as observers from other Directorates General and Cedefop; after 2014, representatives from European associations for universities and VET providers were also present. Its main task was to develop a strategic framework and an overarching concept and communication strategy for ESCO.

The *ESCO Maintenance Committee* (2011-2022) is an expert group consisting (a. a.) of representatives of state employment agencies, statistical institutions, chambers of commerce and industry as well as actors with specific technical expertise. The main task of the Maintenance Committee was to advise the Commission on content and quality assurance. In contrast to the ESCO Board, the Maintenance Committee is located more on a *strategic-conceptual level*.

Initial results of the qualitative interviews emphasize the role of the *ESCO Secretariat* as a central steering body in terms of content and administration. The ESCO Secretariat consist of

various experts who cover the areas of "skills" and "taxonomies". In particular, close cooperation was envisaged with service providers commissioned with the development of the technical infrastructure of ESCO (cf. European Commission, Stakeholder Note 2010).

The ESCO Secretariat is described as "*the brain of the project*" (Member ESCO Board, 02). It is composed of experts with a high level of expertise. Important tasks of the Secretariat contain *content-related and administrative project management*. This includes support and advice to other ESCO bodies as well as the organisation of the working level, a. a. the Mapping of national classifications with the ESCO classification. The cooperation and collaboration were described as very intensive and useful by experts at the implementation level. (ESCO Implementers, 03, 05). Furthermore, the ESCO Secretariat organised the exchange of different ESCO bodies and stakeholders. Other important functions of the ESCO Secretariat are the further development and updating of the classification and platform.

Working level: Representatives with sector-specific expertise were involved in the constitutional process within the framework of *Sectoral Reference Groups (SREF)*. Members of the *Cross-Sectoral Reference Group (CSREF)* were concerned with cross-sectoral competences. This group developed a thesaurus of cross-sectoral skills and competences that can be used to develop occupational profiles (until 2015).

Since 2015 representatives of the individual member states were involved in the *Member States Working Group (MSWG)*. The mandate and task of the MSWG are to disseminate and implement ESCO at the national level on the basis of the EURES Regulation. The Maintenance Committee and MSWG were coordinated by the Commission (cf. committee minutes).

Coordination

In the period from 2011 to 2013, eleven expert groups met within the framework of the Sectoral Reference Groups to develop sectoral classifications of occupations, skills, competences and knowledge. In 2015, further 16 sectors were added. This process was coordinated by the ESCO Secretariat (SEC) and the Taxonomy Expert Group (TEC). This also included the appointment of experts. Consultations on the development of occupational classifications, interoperability with national classifications and a linguistically formulated version of the ESCO skills pillar took place between 2011 and 2017.

The coordination of the sectoral reference groups established for the period 2011-2015 to develop occupational classifications, skills, competences and knowledge for their respective sectors took place on the basis of regular meetings of these expert groups in Brussels (cf. Annen et al., 2020).

The analysed documents suggest a coordination process between the European Commission and the member states including meetings of the working groups of the co-member states as well as "soft" forms of coordination through consultation and negotiation (cf. Annen et al., 2020).

Interviewed members of different ESCO committees and working groups report a regular exchange between the different ESCO bodies and working groups, especially in the first period. This also included an exchange between the conceptual ESCO steering level and the working level, for instance, members of sectors reference groups reporting in meetings of the Maintenance Committee. In the later process, one interviewee noted a rather sporadic interaction between the committees (Member ESCO Board, 02).

On a working level, there was a regular exchange between the different working groups. This was partly initiated by the groups themselves. The general flow of information was primarily mediated by the ESCO Secretariat. Due to its composition, the ESCO Secretariat also had an important function in the consultative processes.

In terms of consultation, one interviewee stressed the problem of information asymmetry in the development process. Due to the complexity of the ESCO development process,

especially in terms of technical issues, several Committee Members had a hard time trying to understand suggestions, ideas and concepts provided by technical experts. In the interview, he emphasizes the role of technical experts within the development process. He, therefore, concludes that the Maintenance Committee was not really a steering committee but rather decoration (*"Etiquette"*) in a commission-driven project (Member ESCO Maintenance Committee, 03).

The steering function of the Commission in the form of the ESCO Secretariat is also described by a former member of the intersectoral working group. The flow of information with the secretariat was *"already linked to the narrative and the idea (...) that the secretariat somehow has its own policy. It has its own idea of what ESCO should actually become and how it should be dealt with. We weren't even necessarily sure whether the Board would follow the same strategy as the Secretariat"* (Member Cross-Sectoral Reference Group, 08).

The preliminary results on the one hand show the exchange, consultation and negotiation of the different ESCO actors, especially in the early development periods. At the same time, however, the central coordination and steering function of the Commission in the form of the ESCO Secretariat also becomes visible.

Change in ESCO Governance in 2015

In 2015, the reference groups were abolished with the launch of the first ESCO version V0. Instead, a broad monitoring committee was formed with the Member State Working Groups. The formal argument for this, according to one interviewee, was that the essential steps had been completed (Member ESCO Board, 02). Another committee member reports that the reference groups were dissolved *"because it was a bit too chaotic to work only with interest representatives who were supposed to build up a taxonomy. They really wanted to rely on, yes, I think, professional taxonomists from the ESCO secretariat"* (Member ESCO Maintenance Committee, 04). With the abolition of the Reference Groups, the ESCO stakeholders seem to play a more important role in the further development of ESCO's content.

In the following years, the ESCO Secretariat organised and coordinated the mapping process in which the member states matched their national classifications with the ESCO classification. The ESCO Secretariat is also in charge of the content and administrative organisation of pilot projects for the ESCO Qualifications Pillar. The project logic in ESCO governance, in which the ESCO Secretariat is responsible for project management, thus seems to have been further strengthened.

5 Conclusion

Initial results of the analyses show a diverse interweaving of governance forms through binding legal acts, soft legislation and the financial support of action programs, which are supposed to support the development and implementation of ESCO. Due to the linking of the labour market and education policy - in this case, through the linking of ESCO and EURES - a greater depth of intervention through binding legal acts (regulations, resolutions) seems to exist within the area of European vocational training policy, which usually is located within the framework of "soft law". In this respect, however, it will be important how and in which manner qualification profiles will be linked to the ESCO occupations and skills. This process has not yet been completed at the present time.

With regard to governance in the ESCO construction process, the analysed documents suggest a differentiated approach of the Commission, in which the (steering) mechanisms in the context of EURES and VET differ. While in the EURES context a rather hierarchical regulation through regulations and decisions becomes visible, the coordination process between the European Commission and the member states includes consultations and meetings of the working groups of the member states as well as "soft" forms of coordination through consultation and

negotiation. However, preliminary interview analyses also address an asymmetry of information between different actors in the construction process, which may have led to problems in the action coordination.

In the coordination process, different logics, as well as discrepancies in the understanding or interpretation of roles and missions of the different actors, become apparent: on the one hand, the project logic from the point of view of the Commission and, on the other, a conflicting logic between education and labour market policy. The increasing technicality of the ESCO project also impacted the coordination and revealed tensions in terms of policy objectives between national and European actors.

Initial results indicate a discrepancy between education policy actors, who are used to acting in the context of “soft law” and Commission actors from a labour market perspective located in the EURES context. This partly seems to lead to conflicting expectations, as the aforementioned interviews indicate. Regarding the question, if ESCO can be seen as a prototype of new European governance between “hard law” and “soft law” the results so far tend to speak against a new form of governance. Rather, the project's strong reference to EURES and the labour market shows that hierarchical forms of governance have become more relevant in this specific context.

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